

Online and Self-paced Learning Measures

Lessons Learned from Designing and Delivering Flexible Training Formats

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Consortium members

Acronym	Partner
EMBL	EUROPEAN MOLECULAR BIOLOGY LABORATORY
BIOBYTE	BIOBYTE SOLUTIONS GMBH
HPCNOW	HPC NOW CONSULTING SL
UO	UNIVERSITETET I OSLO
UB	UNIVERSITAT DE BARCELONA
ZBMED	INFORMATION CENTRE FOR LIFE SCIENCE
Rlcapacity	Rlcapacity
ALU-FR	ALBERT-LUDWIGS-UNIVERSITAET FREIBURG
EPFL	ECOLE POLYTECHNIQUE FEDERALE DE LAUSANNE

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Project Overview

The BioNT consortium is dedicated to providing a comprehensive training program and fostering a community for digital skills relevant to the biotechnology industry and biomedical sector. With a curriculum tailored for both beginners and advanced professionals, BioNT aims to equip individuals with the necessary expertise in handling, processing, and visualising biological data, as well as utilising computational biology tools. Leveraging the consortium's strong background in digital literacy training and extensive network of collaborations, BioNT is poised to professionalise life sciences data management, processing, and analysis skills.

Introduction and Purpose

Over the past years, BioNT has systematically invested in the development of online learning formats and self-paced training materials. The goal is to provide flexible, accessible and sustainable training opportunities for researchers, while ensuring that learning materials remain usable beyond individual events.

This report serves two main purposes. First, it documents BioNT's experiences and lessons learned in designing and delivering online live training as well as in producing self-paced learning materials. Second, it aims to enable other communities and training providers to benefit from these experiences beyond the BioNT context.

The intended audience includes:

- Training providers who are just starting to develop online learning offers, particularly those without an established community infrastructure to draw on
- Trainers outside the data science community who are new to digital and remote teaching formats
- Start-ups and SMEs seeking to train staff internally, including those operating within [Digital Europe](#) or [LEADS](#) project contexts

Why BioNT Invests in Flexible Learning Formats

Researchers increasingly work across institutions, countries and time zones. Fixed, in-person training formats alone can no longer meet these needs. Online live training enables broad participation with low barriers to entry, while self-paced learning supports sustainable knowledge acquisition independent of fixed schedules.

By combining both approaches, BioNT follows a learning vision that emphasises openness, reuse and inclusivity. Training activities are designed not only to transfer knowledge but also to support long-term learning processes and the reuse of educational resources.

BioNT's Learning Vision and Training Ecosystem

BioNT's training ecosystem consists of synchronous online workshops and asynchronous self-paced learning materials derived from these events. Core principles include open educational resources, clearly defined learning outcomes, transparent prerequisites and alignment with FAIR principles for training materials.

A strong emphasis is placed on reusability, both within BioNT and for external communities seeking to adapt or build upon the provided resources. Equally important is the structure of the workshops themselves: the design is deliberately efficient, providing enough scaffolding for participants to follow and engage without requiring constant instructor guidance.

Five Lessons Learned from Online Live Training

BioNT's strongest experience lies in the design and delivery of synchronous online training formats that deliberately restrict direct verbal and visual interaction between participants and trainers. In these courses, participants do not have access to microphones or cameras. Instead, all interaction is mediated through a collaboratively edited document, commonly referred to as "the pad".

This setup represents a core design decision that distinguishes BioNT's approach from many conventional online training formats. When this model was first introduced, it was met with scepticism: the absence of cameras and microphones seemed to risk making training feel cold or one-directional. In practice, the opposite proved true. The combination of a well-staffed helpdesk available before the training (to help participants with technical setup) and dedicated helpers actively responding in the document during sessions created a genuinely responsive and inclusive learning environment.

The primary motivation for this model is to ensure privacy, reduce technical barriers and create an environment that works equally well for participants from academia, industry, SMEs and job seekers. At the same time, it enables structured interaction at scale.

Pad based interaction as the central communication channel

A collaborative document functions as the single point of interaction throughout the course. It serves simultaneously as a communication channel, a space for hands-on activities, a feedback mechanism and a persistent learning resource. Participants ask questions, report issues and provide feedback exclusively through this document.

This approach requires careful document design. Clearly structured sections, predefined interaction boxes and consistent visual cues guide participants and lower the threshold for active participation. Hands-on boxes allow participants to indicate progress, request help or describe issues, while question boxes are used to assess understanding and gather feedback.

Separation of roles enables scalable support

The restriction of direct interaction makes a clear separation of roles essential. Instructors focus exclusively on delivering the training content, while helpers monitor the collaborative document and provide written support to participants in real time.

Helpers answer questions directly in the document, highlight issues that require instructor attention and escalate critical problems when necessary. This role distribution allows instructors to maintain a coherent teaching flow while ensuring that participants receive timely support. Crucially, helpers are not passive monitors; they actively shape the quality of each session.

Real time support without interrupting the teaching flow

Providing real-time support remains essential, even without verbal interaction. The collaborative document enables parallel support without disrupting the session. Participants can continue working while helpers respond, which reduces pressure on both sides and accommodates different learning speeds.

Issues that require immediate attention can be flagged for the instructor, while less urgent feedback is collected and addressed during breaks. This mechanism has proven effective in maintaining momentum during long online sessions.

Continuous feedback and adaptive pacing

Live feedback is collected directly in the collaborative document through short questions, progress indicators and explicit speed checks. This allows instructors to adjust pacing and depth based on participant responses, even in the absence of verbal cues.

Compared to in person workshops, breaks and exercises require more deliberate planning. Flexible break times are negotiated through the document, and exercises are structured so that progress and difficulties become visible at a glance.

Persistence and reuse as an added benefit

An important benefit of the pad based interaction model is persistence. The collaborative document captures questions, answers and reflections throughout the course. After the session, selected content is moved to a history document that remains available to participants as a reference.

This persistence not only supports learning beyond the live event but also provides a strong foundation for transforming live courses into self-paced learning materials.

Five Lessons Learned for Successful Self-Paced Learning

BioNT's experience with self-paced learning builds directly on the design and delivery of online live training. Self-paced materials are not developed independently but are derived from recorded courses and their generated learning material

The central challenge lies in transforming time bound, instructor led sessions into coherent learning experiences that can be followed independently. This requires both conceptual restructuring and technical post processing.

Interaction limited by design to enable reuse

A key prerequisite for successful self-paced learning is the intentional limitation of participant interaction during live courses. By routing all interaction through a collaborative document, questions, feedback and issues are already captured in a reusable written form.

This design decision significantly reduces the effort required to repurpose live training into self-paced formats, as no verbal discussions need to be reconstructed or contextualized afterwards.

Reuse of materials with didactic adaptation

Existing materials from live courses can often be reused for self-paced learning. However, they require targeted adaptation to function without real time instructor support.

Self-assessment elements and reflection prompts are essential additions, enabling learners to evaluate their understanding and progress independently. Ensuring compliance with FAIR principles further supports reuse beyond the original training context.

Post processing as a structured workflow

Transforming live training outputs into self-paced learning materials requires a clearly defined post processing workflow. Recordings, slides, exercises and collaborative documents must be curated and combined into coherent learning units.

Without such a workflow, materials remain fragmented and difficult to navigate for independent learners.

Clear descriptions to support autonomous learning

Meaningful descriptions of course content are critical in self-paced settings. Learners must be able to assess whether a course fits their needs before engaging with the material.

Explicit learning outcomes, prerequisites and required skills provide essential orientation and reduce uncertainty for learners without access to instructors.

Making learning progress visible

An aspect not yet fully implemented but identified as highly valuable is the visibility of learning progress. In self-paced formats, learners benefit from clear signals that acknowledge completed work.

Possible approaches include quizzes with scoring mechanisms, progress indicators or certificates issued upon course completion. Such elements help sustain motivation and give structure to longer learning paths. BioNT intends to explore these approaches in upcoming iterations of its self-paced offerings.

Conclusion

BioNT's blended learning strategy, combining online live training with self-paced formats, has proven effective in reaching diverse audiences and producing reusable training materials. Several design decisions, in particular the pad-based interaction model, have consistently enabled scalable and inclusive learning experiences that would have been difficult to achieve through conventional online formats.

At the same time, honest reflection on what did not work or where challenges remain is equally important, especially for communities starting out with similar approaches.

What proved more difficult than expected:

- The post-processing pipeline for self-paced materials is labour-intensive and requires dedicated time that is easy to underestimate in project planning.
- Progress visibility for self-paced learners remains unsolved: without certificates or scoring mechanisms, it is difficult to know whether participants have genuinely worked through the material.
- Defining and reaching the right target audience requires continuous effort. Without active outreach, well-designed materials can go unnoticed.
- The pad-based interaction model requires upfront investment in document design and helper coordination that is not immediately obvious to new trainers.

What we would do differently:

- Establish the post-processing workflow before running the first course, not after.
- Plan for dedicated helper capacity from the start; this role is easily underestimated.
- Invest earlier in learner-facing progress indicators to improve motivation and completion in self-paced formats.

By sharing these lessons, BioNT aims to lower the barrier for other communities and training providers exploring flexible learning formats. We encourage adaptation, critique and dialogue. These materials are intended as a starting point, not a blueprint.